

Abstract

Octue is an open-source organisation whose mission is to help scientists and engineers become more effective at working with data.

Aerosense is a project developing a MEMS-based surface pressure and acoustic measurement system for wind turbine blades to help:

- Wind turbine manufacturers optimise the aerodynamic design of large, flexible rotors
- Wind farm owner/operators detect faults and optimise operation

The Data Gateway is a fundamental part of this. It comprises a turbine-based python app that collects, parses, and uploads sensor data to the cloud; a serverless Cloud Function that pre-processes and sends this data to Google BigQuery; and the BigQuery database itself. From here, the data can be accessed anywhere in the world for further analysis, dashboarding, and monitoring using any language. The system is highly scalable and available.

Objectives

Data collection and analysis

- Collect data from multiple sensor nodes placed on turbine blades
- Automatically upload sensor data to the cloud at regular, frequent intervals
- Allow easy, retrieval of data from the cloud for analysis and visualisation

Control

- Control the sensor nodes interactively or via automated routines

Resilience and scalability

- Store data at the turbine to upload later in case of internet or power outage
- Use as little energy and hardware as possible

Obstacles and solutions

Buffer overflow (data loss) arose when high bandwidth sensors (e.g. microphones) were added. This was due to the uploader taking enough processor capacity on each upload that the limited serial port buffer filled up faster than it could be emptied by the reader. To fix this, the Gateway was parallelised. The reader's CPU usage was isolated from the uploader's by giving both their own process – the reader could now constantly empty data from the serial port into a process-safe queue while the uploader worked in parallel.

Automation reliability was significantly improved by switching from GitLab to GitHub. This enabled easier automatic code quality checks, automatic cross-platform testing (Linux, MacOS, Windows), and automated releases.

Method

- The Gateway runs on a Raspberry Pi at the base of the tower. Raw data is collected from multiple blade nodes via Bluetooth, buffered in the serial port, parsed, and streamed to the cloud.
- A versatile command line interface (CLI) was developed to run on the Raspberry Pi (in the field) or on researchers' laptops (in the lab) enabling quick and easy interaction with the sensors (sending commands and reading data) and providing the cloud uploader.
- Local storage and daemonisation of the Gateway were added to address power and internet outages.
- A process was implemented for registering installations and generating long-lived authentication credentials unique to each Gateway. This enabled fine-grained access control while allowing devices to be deployed for long periods of time through significant outage durations (i.e. no ability to refresh bearer-type access tokens).
- Cloud Functions (serverless apps) were developed to "spin up" when data is uploaded to preprocess it and send it to BigQuery, and "spin down" when finished. This:
 - Minimises costs (there is zero cost when no data is being uploaded)
 - Maximises scalability (more instances can spin up as more data is uploaded and more wind turbines deploy a Data Gateway).
 - Prevents extreme cost spirals in the event of a malicious DDOS-like attack or other malfunction.
- A Google BigQuery database (data lake) was set up with a schema designed to store raw measurements in a versatile way, enabling new sensors or data types to be added without frequent intervention at the database.
- Finally, materialised views were added to restructure the raw data dynamically, enabling easy and intuitive querying using basic SQL, Pandas/Numpy, and dashboarding tools.
- The open-source Octue SDK was used to provide simple and easy authenticated data upload to the cloud.

Conclusion

A fully-tested, open-source, production-ready example of turbine blade data collection, cloud ingress, and data lake storage (together with documentation) has been developed and made available to the community.

The Aerosense Data Gateway brings this all together to provide an out-of-the-box solution to monitoring wind turbines in the field and collecting blade data for research. This allows wind energy scientists to focus on what they do best – wind energy research – instead of software engineering and DevOps.

Full code and documentation is available here:

- Data Gateway – <https://github.com/aerosense-ai/data-gateway>
- Octue SDK – <https://github.com/octue/octue-sdk-python>

What next?

- Field testing the Gateway with multiple sensor nodes
- Automated comparison of data from the Gateway with OpenFAST analyses of the same turbines via an [OpenFAST digital twin](#)

Come to our talk: Friday, 24 June 2022, 9:00 - 10:15 in the Auditorium

MEET US AT "From Blade to BigQuery" (Monitoring and Diagnostics session) on Friday!

Replace
with QR code

Replace
with QR code